
pcDNA5/FRT-BSG(CD147)-mut-NtoQ-HA-TEV-Halo

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-pcDNA5Rev_D10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-CMV-F_C10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_2-pcDNA-Rev_C10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_5-pcDNA-Rev_D10.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B4-Halo-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B5-Halo-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F1.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F2.seq

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F3.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F4.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F5.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F6.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-CMV-Fwd.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F1.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F2.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F3.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CMV-seq-Fwd.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-HA-Halo_E1-CMV-seq-Fwd.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-HA-Halo_E1-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 pcDNA5FRT-CMV-CD147-Halo-mut1_U2-Halo-seq-R ev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CMV-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-Halo-seq-R ev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CMV-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-Halo-seq-R ev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CMV-CD147-Halo-mut2_V1-Halo-seq-R ev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P6.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P5.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P7.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P6.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P3.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P5.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P7.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P3.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P7.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P5.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P6.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-P3.ab1

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut1_U1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-CMV-Fwd.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P7.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P6.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P5.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P3.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-Halo-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-mut2_V2-P4.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ_Mut2_B1-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ_Mut1_A1-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ_Mut1_A2-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ_Mut2_B2-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dual_C2-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dual_C2-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dual_C1-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dual_C1-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P3.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P5.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P3.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P6.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P6.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-CMV-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab
1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P7.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P7.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P3.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-Rev.ab
1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-Halo-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P5.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P4.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P5.ab1

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P6.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P7.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P5.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P7.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-CMV-Fwd.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P4.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P3.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-P6.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-Halo-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_A1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P6.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P5.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P3.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P4.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-pcDNA5-P7.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-Halo-Rev.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_B1-CMV-Fwd.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P5.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-Rev.ab
1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P4.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P6.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P7.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-pcDNA5-P3.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-CMV-Fwd.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo_NtoQ_C2-Halo-Rev.ab1](#)

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dualmut_C6-CMV-seq-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-mut1_A3-Halo-seq-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-mut1_A3-CMV-seq-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-mut1_A4-Halo-seq-Rev.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dualmut_C5-Halo-seq-Rev_R.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dualmut_C5-CMV-seq-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-mut1_A4-CMV-seq-Fwd.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD147-Halo-NtoQ-dualmut_C6-Halo-seq-Rev.ab1